

1 **The HSC transcriptome is enriched for the expression of IBD risk factors.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the HSC to determine without bias, with reference to the keratinocyte
8 and the fibroblast, HSC signature genes. The analysis revealed a preponderance of IBD (inflammatory
9 bowel disease)-associated genes. These genes included WAS, TAGAP, as well as a group of Sh3-domain
10 factors. The total number of IBD risk factors genes enriched within the HSC transcriptome and relative
11 position of the genes within the HSC transcriptome suggested specific importance of an HSC function in
12 IBD.

13 Citations

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